

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part IV

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Four new dyes have been prepared by condensing the 7-iodothioindoxyl with cinnamaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, and vanillin, respectively. Their dyeing and other properties have been studied and compared with those of analogous 5-iodo dyes.

The present work was undertaken to study the effect of introducing an iodine atom in the 7-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of substituted benzylidene derivatives and for comparing these with the corresponding 5-iodo derivatives¹.

The required dyes have been prepared by condensation of 7-iodothioindoxyl with anisaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, and vanillin, respectively.

The dyes dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid, forming a red or dark red solution and the original dyes are reprecipitated on dilution with water.

TABLE I

*Compound.	Shade on cotton.	λ_{max}^{py}	Log ϵ .
Anisylidene-2-(7-iodo)-T	Light yellow	448 m μ	4.333
Anisylidene-2-(5-iodo)-T	Light yellow	455	4.306
Cinnamylidene-2-(7-iodo)-T	Orange-yellow	402	3.651
Cinnamylidene-2-(5-iodo)-T	Orange-yellow	470	3.268
3'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)-T	Pink	452	4.197
3'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)-T	Pink	402	5.777
4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)-T	Reddish violet	458	4.440
4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)-T	Reddish violet	466	4.408

* T denotes thionaphthene.

The 5-iodo-substituted dyes¹ showed the expected bathochromic shifts when compared with 7-iodo derivatives (Table I).

Though absorptions were examined in pyridine solution on a Hilger Watts' spectrophotometer, the sensitisations were examined on an Adam Hilger Wodge spectrograph, following the usual technique². Some of the dyes of this series³ were found to be photographic sensitisers. The dyes under report, however, do not show any photosensitising property.

The dyeing shades of the compounds were developed on cotton by reduction of the dye by alkaline hydrosulphite and subsequent oxidation. The dyes (I) and (IV) were also found to be resistant to vatting like the corresponding 5-iodo dyes¹.

1. *This Journal*, under publication.
2. Sinha, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 165.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anisylidene-2-(7-iodo)thionaphthene (I).—A solution of anisaldehyde (0.17 g.) and 7-iodothioindoxyl (0.345 g.) in boiling anhydrous ethanol (10 ml) was treated with HCl (conc., 2 ml), when the condensation product separated as a yellow precipitate. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 min., filtered, and washed with ethanol, followed by hot water. The dye (0.37 g.) was then crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 191-92°. (Found: I, 32.30; S, 8.25. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4IS$ requires I, 32.23; S, 8.12%).

Cinnamylidene-2-(7-iodo)thionaphthene (II).—The dye was similarly separated as an orange-red product from boiling anhydrous ethanol (10 ml) solution of cinnamaldehyde (0.198 g.) and 7-iodothioindoxyl (0.41 g.) and HCl (conc., 2 ml). The compound (0.44 g.) was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 144-45° (shrinking at 120°). (Found: I, 32.62; S, 7.98. $C_{17}H_{11}OIS$ requires I, 32.56; S, 8.20%).

3'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)thionaphthene (III).—The dye was obtained from 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.16 g.) and 7-iodothioindoxyl (0.345 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (15 ml) solution and HCl (conc., 1.5 ml) on heating for 2 hr. The dye (0.18 g.) was recrystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 219-20°. (Found: I, 33.56; S, 8.51. $C_{15}H_9O_4IS$ requires I, 33.42; S, 8.42%).

4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)thionaphthene (IV).—On refluxing a mixture of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.17 g.) and 7-iodothioindoxyl (0.30 g.) in hot anhydrous ethanol (10 ml) and HCl (conc., 2 ml) for 40 min. The dye separating (0.346 g.) was recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 178-79°. (Found: I, 31.10; S, 8.00. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3IS$ requires I, 30.97; S, 7.80%).

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